

Parameters in the R-data file

The data in the R-file are obtained from the Paleo Biological Data Base <https://dev.paleobiodb.org/data1.2/> by applying the command:

```
https://paleobiodb.org/data1.2/occs/list.csv?datainfo&rowcount&interval=Ediacaran,Holocene&show=class,classtxt,genus,subgenus,abund,coll,coords,loc,paleoloc,strat,stratxt,lith,env,ref,crmod,timebins,timecompare
```

The time interval for which data are extracted is Ediacaran to the Holocene. As seen from the above command, 18 parameters are used in the call.

The meaning of these parameters are:

Parameters	Meaning
<u>class</u>	The taxonomic classification of the occurrence: phylum, class, order, family, genus.
<u>classtxt</u>	Like class, but also includes the relevant taxon identifiers.
<u>genus</u>	The genus corresponding to each occurrence, if the occurrence has been identified to the genus level. This block is redundant if class or classtxt are used.
<u>subgenus</u>	The genus corresponding to each occurrence, plus the subgenus if any. This can be added to class or classtxt in order to display subgenera, or used instead of genus to display both the genus and the subgenus if any.
<u>abund</u>	Information about the abundance of this occurrence in the collection
<u>coll</u>	The name of the collection in which the occurrence was found, plus any additional remarks entered about it.
<u>loc</u>	Additional information about the geographic locality of the occurrence
<u>coords</u>	The latitude and longitude of this occurrence
<u>strat</u>	Basic information about the stratigraphic context of the occurrence.
<u>stratxt</u>	Detailed information about the stratigraphic context of the occurrence. This includes all of the information from strat plus extra fields.
<u>lith</u>	Basic information about the lithological context of the occurrence.
<u>env</u>	The paleoenvironment associated with the occurrence.
<u>Ref</u>	The reference from which the occurrence was entered, as formatted text. If no reference is recorded for this occurrence, the primary reference for its associated collection is returned.
<u>crmod</u>	The created and modified timestamps for the occurrence record
<u>timebins</u>	Shows a list of temporal bins into which each occurrence falls according to the timerule selected for this request. You may select one using the timerule parameter, or it will default to major.
<u>timecompare</u>	Like timebins, but shows this information for all available timerules.
<u>paleoloc</u>	Information about the paleogeographic locality of the occurrence, evaluated according to the model specified by the parameter pgm.

We will call these parameters command-parameters. They are with colour coding:

```
"class, classtext, genus, subgenus, abund, coll, coords, loc, paleoloc, strat, stratext, lith, env, ref, crmod, timebins, timecompare"
```

Each of the coloured parameters will make the database respond with one to several parameters, which are written to the R-file.

The header of the R-data file is:

```
"Data Provider", "The Paleobiology Database"  
"Data Source", "The Paleobiology Database"  
"Data License", "Creative Commons CC-BY"  
"License URL", "http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/"  
"Documentation URL", "http://paleobiodb.org/data1.2/occs/list_doc.html"  
"Data  
URL", "http://paleobiodb.org/data1.2/occs/list.csv?datainfo&rowcount&interval=E  
diacaran,Holocene&show=class,classtext,genus,subgenus,abund,coll,coords,loc,paleo  
loc,strat,stratext,lith,env,ref,crmod,timebins,timecompare"  
"Access Time", "Sat 2022-04-09 14:16:59 GMT"  
"Title", "PBDB Data Service"  
"Parameters:"  
"", "interval", "Ediacaran,Holocene"  
"", "timerule", "major"  
"", "taxon_status", "all"  
"", "show", "class, classtext, genus, subgenus, abund, coll, coords, loc, paleoloc, strat, s  
tratext, lith, env, ref, crmod, timebins, timecompare"  
"Elapsed Time", "157"  
"Records Found", "1548307"  
"Records Returned", "1548307"  
"Records:"  
"occurrence_no", "record_type", "reid_no", "flags", "collection_no", "identified_nam  
e", "identified_rank", "identified_no", "difference", "accepted_name", "accepted_ran  
k", "accepted_no", "early_interval", "late_interval", "max_ma", "min_ma", "reference  
no", "phylum", "phylum_no", "class", "class_no", "order", "order_no", "family", "family  
no", "genus", "genus_no", "subgenus_no", "abund_value", "abund_unit", "collection_na  
me", "collection_subset", "collection_aka", "lng", "lat", "cc", "state", "county", "lat  
lng_basis", "latlng_precision", "geogscale", "geogcomments", "paleomodel", "paleolng  
", "paleolat", "geoplate", "formation", "stratgroup", "member", "formation", "stratgr  
up", "member", "stratscale", "zone", "localsection", "localbed", "localbedunit", "loca  
lorder", "regionalsection", "regionalbed", "regionalbedunit", "regionalorder", "stra  
tcomments", "lithdescript", "lithology1", "lithification1", "minor_lithology1", "lit  
hology2", "lithification2", "minor_lithology2", "environment", "primary_reference",  
"created", "modified", "time_bins", "time_contain", "time_major", "time_buffer", "tim  
e_overlap"
```

First, several basic parameters are shown above with a green background colour. These parameter will always be provided independent of the command parameters.

The yellow command parameters result in a response with 11 parameters, starting with "phylum" and ending with "subgenus_no" (yellow background). The following cyan-coloured parameter "abund" results in two parameters. And so forth.

The meaning of the parameters is given in the Paleo Biological Data Base <https://dev.paleobiodb.org/data1.2/> and shown below (from the database).

The "Field name" column provides the name of the parameters in the R-file, and the "Block" column names the corresponding command-parameter that generated the "Field name". Finally, the "Description" column gives information on the parameter.

Field name		Block	Description						
pbdb	com								
occurrence_no	oid	basic	A positive integer that uniquely identifies the occurrence						
record_type	typ	basic	The type of this object: occ for an occurrence.						
reid_no	eid	basic	If this occurrence was reidentified, a unique identifier for the reidentification.						
flags	flg	basic	<p>This field will be empty for most records. Otherwise, it will contain one or more of the following letters:</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>R</td> <td>This identification has been superceded by a more recent one. In other words, this occurrence has been reidentified.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>I</td> <td>This identification is an ichnotaxon</td> </tr> <tr> <td>F</td> <td>This identification is a form taxon</td> </tr> </table>	R	This identification has been superceded by a more recent one. In other words, this occurrence has been reidentified.	I	This identification is an ichnotaxon	F	This identification is a form taxon
R	This identification has been superceded by a more recent one. In other words, this occurrence has been reidentified.								
I	This identification is an ichnotaxon								
F	This identification is a form taxon								
collection_no	cid	basic	The identifier of the collection with which this occurrence is associated.						
permissions	prm	basic	<p>The accessibility of this record. If empty, then the record is public. Otherwise, the value of this record will be one of the following:</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>members</td> <td>The record is accessible to database members only.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>authorizer</td> <td>The record is accessible to its authorizer group, and to any other authorizer groups given permission.</td> </tr> <tr> <td>group(...)</td> <td>The record is accessible to members of the specified research group(s) only.</td> </tr> </table>	members	The record is accessible to database members only.	authorizer	The record is accessible to its authorizer group, and to any other authorizer groups given permission.	group(...)	The record is accessible to members of the specified research group(s) only.
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group(...)	The record is accessible to members of the specified research group(s) only.								

identified_name	idn	basic	The taxonomic name by which this occurrence was identified. This field will be omitted for responses in the compact vocabulary if it is identical to the value of <i>accepted_name</i> .
identified_rank	idr	basic	The taxonomic rank of the identified name, if this can be determined. This field will be omitted for responses in the compact vocabulary if it is identical to the value of <i>accepted_rank</i> .
identified_no	iid	basic	The unique identifier of the identified taxonomic name. If this is empty, then the name was never entered into the taxonomic hierarchy stored in this database and we have no further information about the classification of this occurrence. In some cases, the genus has been entered into the taxonomic hierarchy but not the species. This field will be omitted for responses in the compact vocabulary if it is identical to the value of <i>accepted_no</i> .
difference	tdf	basic	If the identified name is different from the accepted name, this field gives the reason why. This field will be present if, for example, the identified name is a junior synonym or nomen dubium, or if the species has been recombined, or if the identification is misspelled.
accepted_name	tna	basic	The value of this field will be the accepted taxonomic name corresponding to the identified name.
accepted_attr	att	attr	The attribution (author and year) of the accepted name
accepted_rank	rnk	basic	The taxonomic rank of the accepted name. This may be different from the identified rank if the identified name is a nomen dubium or otherwise invalid, or if the identified name has not been fully entered into the taxonomic hierarchy of this database.

accepted_no	tid	basic	The unique identifier of the accepted taxonomic name in this database.
early_interval	oei	basic	The specific geologic time range associated with this occurrence (not necessarily a standard interval), or the interval that begins the range if <i>late_interval</i> is also given
late_interval	oli	basic	The interval that ends the specific geologic time range associated with this occurrence, if different from the value of <i>early_interval</i>
max_ma	eag	basic	The early bound of the geologic time range associated with this occurrence (in Ma)
min_ma	lag	basic	The late bound of the geologic time range associated with this occurrence (in Ma)
ref_author	aut	refattr	The author(s) of the reference from which this data was entered.
ref_pubyr	pby	refattr	The year of publication of the reference from which this data was entered
reference_no	rid	basic	The identifier of the reference from which this data was entered
phylum	phl	class	The name of the phylum in which this occurrence is classified.
phylum_no	phn	classext	The identifier of the phylum in which this occurrence is classified. This is only included with the block <i>classext</i> .
class	cll	class	The name of the class in which this occurrence is classified.
class_no	cln	classext	The identifier of the class in which this occurrence is classified. This is only included with the block <i>classext</i> .
order	odl	class	The name of the order in which this occurrence is classified.
order_no	odn	classext	The identifier of the order in which this occurrence is classified. This is only included with the block <i>classext</i> .

family	fml	class	The name of the family in which this occurrence is classified.
family_no	fmn	classext	The identifier of the family in which this occurrence is classified. This is only included with the block <i>classext</i> .
genus	gnl	class	The name of the genus in which this occurrence is classified. If the block <i>subgenus</i> is specified, this will include the subgenus name if any.
genus_no	gnn	classext	The identifier of the genus in which this occurrence is classified
subgenus_no	sgn	classext	The identifier of the subgenus in which this occurrence is classified, if any.
genus	gnl	genus	The name of the genus in which this occurrence is classified. If the block <i>subgenus</i> is specified, this will include the subgenus name if any.
primary_name	idg	ident	The taxonomic name (less species) by which this occurrence was identified. This is often a genus, but may be a higher taxon.
primary_reso	rsg	ident	The resolution of the primary name, i.e. sensu lato or n. gen.
subgenus_name	idf	ident	The subgenus name (if any) by which this occurrence was identified
subgenus_reso	rsf	ident	The resolution of the subgenus name, i.e. aff. or n. subgen.
species_name	ids	ident	The species name (if any) by which this occurrence was identified
species_reso	rss	ident	The resolution of the species name, i.e. cf. or n. sp.
occurrence_comments	ocm	rem	Additional comments about this occurrence, if any.

image_no	img	img	If this value is non-zero, you can use it to construct image URLs using taxa/thumb and taxa/icon .
plant_organ	pl1	plant	The plant organ, if any, associated with this occurrence. This field will be empty unless the occurrence is a plant fossil.
plant_organ2	pl2	plant	An additional plant organ, if any, associated with this occurrence.
abund_value	abv	abund	The abundance of this occurrence within its containing collection
abund_unit	abu	abund	The unit in which this abundance is expressed
taxon_environment	jev	ecospace	The general environment or environments in which this life form is found. See ecotaph vocabulary .
environment_basis	jec	ecospace	Specifies the taxon from which the environment information is inherited.
motility	jmo	ecospace	Whether the organism is motile, attached and/or epibiont, and its mode of locomotion if any. See ecotaph vocabulary .
motility_basis	jmc	etbasis	Specifies the taxon for which the motility information was set. The taphonomy and ecospace information are inherited from parent taxa unless specific values are set.
life_habit	jlh	ecospace	The general life mode and locality of this organism. See ecotaph vocabulary .
life_habit_basis	jhc	etbasis	Specifies the taxon for which the life habit information was set. See motility_basis above. These fields are only included if the ecospace block is also included.
vision	jvs	ecospace	The degree of vision possessed by this organism. See ecotaph vocabulary .
vision_basis	jvc	etbasis	Specifies the taxon for which the vision information was set.

			See motility_basis above. These fields are only included if the ecospace block is also included.
diet	jdt	ecospace	The general diet or feeding mode of this organism. See ecotaph vocabulary .
diet_basis	jdc	etbasis	Specifies the taxon for which the diet information was set. See motility_basis above. These fields are only included if the ecospace block is also included.
reproduction	jre	ecospace	The mode of reproduction of this organism. See ecotaph vocabulary .
reproduction_basis	jrc	etbasis	Specifies the taxon for which the reproduction information was set. See motility_basis above. These fields are only included if the ecospace block is also included.
ontogeny	jon	ecospace	Briefly describes the ontogeny of this organism. See ecotaph vocabulary .
ontogeny_basis	joc	etbasis	Specifies the taxon for which the ontogeny information was set. See motility_basis above. These fields are only included if the ecospace block is also included.
ecospace_comments	jcm	ecospace	Additional remarks about the ecospace, if any.
composition	jco	ttaph	The composition of the skeletal parts of this organism. See taphonomy vocabulary .
architecture	jsa	ttaph	An indication of the internal skeletal architecture. See taphonomy vocabulary .
thickness	jth	ttaph	An indication of the relative thickness of the skeleton. See taphonomy vocabulary .
reinforcement	jsr	ttaph	An indication of the skeletal reinforcement, if any. See taphonomy vocabulary .

taphonomy_basis	jtc	etbasis	Specifies the taxon for which the taphonomy information was set. See motility_basis above. These fields are only included if the otaph block is also included.
collection_name	cnm	coll	An arbitrary name which identifies the collection, not necessarily unique
collection_subset	cns	coll	If the collection is a part of another one, this field specifies which part
collection_aka	aka	coll	An alternate name for the collection, or additional remarks about it.
lng	lng	coords	The longitude at which the occurrence was found (in degrees)
lat	lat	coords	The latitude at which the occurrence was found (in degrees)
cc	cc2	loc	The country in which the collection is located, encoded as ISO-3166-1 alpha-2
state	stp	loc	The state or province in which the collection is located, if known
county	cny	loc	The county or municipal area in which the collection is located, if known
latlng_basis	n/a	loc	The basis of the reported location of the collection. Follow this link for a list of basis and precision codes . This field and the next are only included in responses using the pbdb vocabulary.
latlng_precision	n/a	loc	The precision of the collection coordinates. Follow the above link for a list of the code values.
n/a	prc	loc	A two-letter code indicating the basis and precision of the geographic coordinates. This field is reported instead of latlng_basis and latlng_precision in responses that use the compact vocabulary.

			Follow the above link for a list of the code values.
geogscale	gsc	loc	The geographic scale of the collection.
geogcomments	ggc	loc	Additional comments about the geographic location of the collection
bin_id_3	lv3	bin	The identifier of the level-3 cluster in which the collection or cluster is located
bin_id_2	lv2	bin	The identifier of the level-2 cluster in which the collection or cluster is located
bin_id_1	lv1	bin	The identifier of the level-1 cluster in which the collection or cluster is located
paleomodel	pm1	paleoloc	The primary model specified by the parameter pgm. This field will only be included if more than one model is indicated.
paleolng	pln	paleoloc	The paleolongitude of the collection, evaluated according to the primary model indicated by the parameter pgm.
paleolat	pla	paleoloc	The paleolatitude of the collection, evaluated according to the primary model indicated by the parameter pgm.
geoplate	gpl	paleoloc	The identifier of the geological plate on which the collection lies, evaluated according to the primary model indicated by the parameter pgm. This might be either a number or a string.
paleomodel2	pm2	paleoloc	An alternate model specified by the parameter pgm. This field will only be included if more than one model is indicated. There may also be paleomodel3, etc.
paleolng2	pn2	paleoloc	An alternate paleolongitude for the collection, if the pgm parameter indicates more than one model. There may also be paleolng3, etc.

paleolat2	pa2	paleoloc	An alternate paleolatitude for the collection, if the pgm parameter indicates more than one model. There may also be paleolat3, etc.
geoplate2	gp2	paleoloc	An alternate geological plate identifier, if the pgm parameter indicates more than one model. There may also be geoplate3, etc.
cc	cc2	prot	The country in which the collection is located, encoded as ISO-3166-1 alpha-2
protected	ptd	prot	The protected status of the land on which the collection is located, if known.
cx_int_no	cx_i	time	The identifier of the most specific single interval from the selected timescale that covers the entire time range associated with the collection or cluster.
time_bins	tbi	timebins	A list of time intervals into which this occurrence or collection is placed according to the timerule selected for this operation. You can see which rule is selected by including the datainfo parameter. A value of - means that the time range is too large to match any bin under this timerule.
time_contain	tbc	timecompare	List of time intervals into which this occurrence or collection would be placed according to the contain timerule, or - if the range is too large.
time_major	tbm	timecompare	List of time intervals into which this occurrence or collection would be placed according to the major timerule, or - if the range is too large.
time_buffer	tbb	timecompare	List of time intervals into which this occurrence or collection would be placed according to the buffer timerule, or - if the range is too large.
time_overlap	tbo	timecompare	List of time intervals into which this occurrence or collection would be placed according to the overlap timerule.

formation	sfm	strat	The stratigraphic formation in which the collection is located, if known
stratgroup	sgr	strat	The stratigraphic group in which the collection is located, if known
member	smb	strat	The stratigraphic member in which the collection is located, if known
stratscale	ssc	stratext	The stratigraphic range covered by this collection
zone	szn	stratext	The stratigraphic zone in which the collection is located, if known
localsection	sls	stratext	The local section in which the collection is located, if known
localbed	slb	stratext	The local bed in which the collection is located, if known
localorder	slo	stratext	The order in which local beds were described, if known
regionalsection	srs	stratext	The regional section in which the collection is located, if known
regionalbed	srb	stratext	The regional bed in which the collection is located, if known
regionalorder	sro	stratext	The order in which regional beds were described, if known
stratcomments	scm	stratext	Additional comments about the stratigraphic context of the collection, if any
lithdescript	ldc	lith	Detailed description of the collection site in terms of lithology
lithology1	lt1	lith	The first lithology described for the collection site; the database can represent up to two different lithologies per collection
lithadj1	la1	lithext	Adjective(s) describing the first lithology
lithification1	lf1	lith	Lithification state of the first lithology described for the site

minor_lithology1	lm1	lith	Minor lithology associated with the first lithology described for the site
fossilsfrom1	ff1	lithext	Whether or not fossils were taken from the first described lithology
lithology2	lt2	lith	The second lithology described for the collection site, if any
lithadj2	la2	lithext	Adjective(s) describing the second lithology, if any
lithification2	lf2	lith	Lithification state of the second lithology described for the site. See above for values.
minor_lithology2	lm2	lith	Minor lithology associated with the second lithology described for the site, if any
fossilsfrom2	ff2	lithext	Whether or not fossils were taken from the second described lithology
collection_type	cct	methods	The type or purpose of the collection.
collection_methods	ccx	methods	The method or methods employed.
museum	ccu	methods	The museum or museums which hold the specimens.
collection_coverage	ccv	methods	Fossils that were present but not specifically listed.
collection_size	ccs	methods	The number of fossils actually collected.
rock_censused	ccr	methods	The amount of rock censused.
collectors	ccc	methods	Names of the collectors.
collection_dates	ccd	methods	Dates on which the collection was done.
collection_comments	ccm	methods	Comments about the collecting methods.
taxonomy_comments	tcm	methods	Comments about the taxonomy of what was found.
environment	env	env	The paleoenvironment associated with the collection site
environment	env	geo	The paleoenvironment of the collection site

tectonic_setting	tec	geo	The tectonic setting of the collection site
geology_comments	gcm	geo	General comments about the geology of the collection site
pres_mode	tpm	ctaph	This field reports the modes of preservation, occurrence, and mineralization from the 'Preservation' tab on the PBDB collection form.
preservation_quality	tpq	ctaph	Quality of the anatomical detail preserved.
spatial_resolution	tps	ctaph	Spatial resolution of the preservation information.
temporal_resolution	tpt	ctaph	Temporal resolution of the preservation information.
lagerstätten	tpl	ctaph	Type of lagerstätten found in this collection.
concentration	tpc	ctaph	Degree of concentration of the fossils found in this collection.
orientation	tpo	ctaph	Orientation of the fossil(s) found in this collection.
abund_in_sediment	tpa	ctaph	Abundance in sediment
sorting	tpr	ctaph	Degree of size sorting
fragmentation	tpf	ctaph	Degree of fragmentation
bioerosion	tpb	ctaph	Degree of bioerosion
encrustation	tpe	ctaph	Degree of encrustation
preservation_comments	pcm	ctaph	Preservation comments, if any.
assembl_comps	cps	comps	The size classes found in this collection. The value of this field will be one or more of: macrofossils, mesofossils, microfossils.
articulated_parts	cpa	comps	The prevalence of articulated body parts in this collection.
associated_parts	cpb	comps	The prevalence of associated body parts in this collection.

common_body_parts	cpc	comps	A list of body parts that are common in this collection.
rare_body_parts	cpd	comps	A list of body parts that are rare in this collection.
feed_pred_traces	cpt	comps	A list of feeding/predation traces found in this collection, if any.
artifacts	cpf	comps	A list of artifacts found in this collection, if any.
component_comments	acm	comps	Component comments, if any.
primary_reference	ref	ref	The primary reference associated with this record (as formatted text)
research_group	rgp	resgroup	The research group(s), if any, associated with this collection.
authorizer_no	ati	ent, entname	The identifier of the person who authorized the entry of this record
enterer_no	eni	ent, entname	The identifier of the person who actually entered this record.
modifier_no	mdi	ent, entname	The identifier of the person who last modified this record, if it has been modified.
authorizer	ath	entname	The name of the person who authorized the entry of this record
enterer	ent	entname	The name of the person who actually entered this record
modifier	mdf	entname	The name of the person who last modified this record, if it has been modified.
created	dcr	crmod	The date and time at which this record was created.
modified	dmd	crmod	The date and time at which this record was last modified.

As the R-program runs it makes an additional reduction of the number of parameters to:

Parameter
"collection_no",
"collection_name",
"identified_rank",
"identified_name",
"accepted_name",
"accepted_rank",
"early_interval",
"late_interval",
"max_ma",
"min_ma",
"reference_no",
"phylum",
"class",
"order",
"family",
"genus",
"lng",
"lat",
"paleolng",
"paleolat",
"formation",
"lithology1",
"lithification1",
"environment",
"created",
"zone"

Details of the functions and the statistics performed in the program can be found in <https://github.com/divDyn/ddPhanero/tree/master/doc>